

Electrical Conductivity Behaviour, Kinetic and Thermodynamic Studies on $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{CuS}-\text{Cr}_2\text{S}_3$ Systems

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Samples of $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{CuS}-\text{Cr}_2\text{S}_3$ were characterised by chemical, ir and X-ray diffraction analysis. Electrical conductivity measurements were carried out in the temperature range, room temperature to 350° . $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ system was found to be *n*-type semiconductor, $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ system *p*-type semiconductor while $\text{CuS}-\text{Cr}_2\text{S}_3$ system is a metallic conductor. The $\ln\sigma$ vs $1/T$ plots were single straight lines whereas $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ system gave a break at about 200° (T_b) that could be due to a change in the semiconducting nature of the solid. The activation energies for electrical conductivity were calculated according to the linear regression analysis. On increasing the calcination temperature for the oxide systems the rate constant for catalytic decomposition of H_2O , decreased while for the sulphide system it increased. The activation energies were calculated.

Spinel is a large class of compounds of considerable industrial interest as well as interesting structural and electrical properties¹. These properties are controlled by the nature of ions, their charge and site distribution amongst the tetrahedral and octahedral sites. The electrical conductivity of some spinels could be arranged in the following order: aluminate < chromites < ferrites². It was shown³ that the electrical conductivities of CuRb_2S_4 , CuRb_2Se_4 , CuV_2S_4 , CuCo_2S_4 and CuTi_2S_4 have a metallic conduction independent of the temperature. The reported study⁴ on the electrical conductivity of $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ and the occurrence of breaks in the $\log\sigma$ vs $1/T$ plots at 190 and 360° for samples calcined at 650° is attributed to phase transformation from the tetragonally distorted form to cubic form.

Measurements to determine the kinetics of decomposition of H_2O were made, since the decisive factor governing the catalytic activity of a number of oxide and sulphide systems⁵ is the oxidation state of the catalytically active component. Accordingly, $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{CuS}-\text{Cr}_2\text{S}_3$ systems were selected for the present study to throw some light and give further information on their spinel structures and activities.

Results and discussion

The ir spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system heated to constant weight at 110° show a broad band at $3250-3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and also two wide peaks at $430-690\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The broad band is characteristic for the OH group while the other two wide peaks may be due to the $\text{Fe}^{3+}-\text{O}^{2-}$ bond. The $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ samples calcined for 5 h at 500 , 600 , 700 and 800° respectively, show a change for the two wide peaks slightly with increasing calcination temperature that could be due to the change of $\text{Fe}^{3+}-\text{O}^{2-}$

distances for octahedral and tetrahedral complexes confirming an inverse spinel structure. For sample calcined at 800° the disappearance of the broad band at $3500-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be attributed to the absence of coordinated water molecule while the appearance of two peaks at 600 and 410 cm^{-1} could be assigned to the tetrahedral and octahedral complexes⁶ respectively. The ir spectra of $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ system reveal that $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2-\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dried to constant weight at 110° shows a broad band at $3500-3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and another band at 1380 cm^{-1} that could be attributed to OH group of the coordinated water molecules and $\text{Cr}^{3+}-\text{O}^{2-}$ bond respectively. The ir spectra of the $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ system calcined at 500 , 600 , 700 and 800° respectively, show a peak at 1390 cm^{-1} and two bands at 600 and 510 cm^{-1} that did not change to either higher or lower frequencies as the calcination temperature increases. These could be attributed to the normal spinel structure that agrees with the other chromite spinel⁷. Also the two bands at 600 and 510 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the tetrahedral and octahedral complexes respectively.

The X-ray diffraction patterns for $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ systems have been studied. The diffraction patterns of Fe_2O_3 , Cr_2O_3 and CuO were found to be not affected by the calcination temperature. For the $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ system calcined at 500° , and according to the ASTM card⁸, the characteristic *d*-lines of CuO (2.72 , 2.52 , 2.31 and $1.85\text{ \AA}$) and those of Fe_2O_3 (2.69 , 2.5 and $1.7\text{ \AA}$) as well as that of lines of copper ferrite spinel (2.95 , 2.5 and $1.5\text{ \AA}$) are well illustrated in the X-ray diffraction patterns. For samples calcined at 600 , 700 and 800° , the *d*-lines for the spinel increases in intensity with increasing calcination temperature above 600° where the reactivity is high enough to form copper ferrite ($\text{Cu}^{2+}\text{Fe}^{3+}\text{O}_4^{2-}$). For the $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ system and

according to the ASTM cards⁹, the diffraction lines having d -values of 4.87, 2.56, 2.40 and 1.63 Å are attributed to the formation of CuCr_2O_4 . For sample calcined at 500°, the intensity of these lines are high enough, that the formation of CuCr_2O_4 goes at a measurable rate⁹. At 800°, the X-ray diffraction lines characteristic for CuO and Cr_2O_3 disappear indicating almost complete formation of CuCr_2O_4 .

Electrical conductivity: Electrical conductivities were measured for $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{S}_3$ systems which were calcined at different temperature as mentioned above. For the $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ system, Fig. 1 shows the plots of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$. Straight lines are obtained with one break

Fig 1 Arrhenius plots of electrical conductivity of $\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ mixture calcined at: (—○—) 500°, (—●—) 600°, (—△—) 700 and (—×—) 800°.

(T_b) at 165, 170, 195 and $205 \pm 5^\circ$ for samples calcined at 500, 600, 700 and 800° respectively. It indicates that T_b value increases as the calcination temperature increases. This behaviour could be attributed to the change in semiconductor nature of solids¹⁰ and may be interpreted in terms of change in cationic distribution of the magnetic ions Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} between A (interstitial) and B (normal sites) in copper ferrite lattice¹¹. The activation energy values E_{a1} , E_{a2} calculated by the regression method for samples below and above T_b respectively, are reported in Table 1. The variation in their values suggests the existence of two different mechanisms for conduction. For the same system, Krishnamurthy *et al.*⁴ reported two breaks (T_b) at 190 and 360°. There are evidences^{4,12} to indicate that

CuFe_2O_4 at low temperature below T_b shows p -type conduction while it becomes n -type at high temperature⁴. The reported activation energy⁴ for electrical conductivity of CuFe_2O_4 is 11.5 below T_b and 22.0 kJ above T_b . These values are lower than those in the present study which may be due to difference in the conditions of sample preparation and measurements.

TABLE 1—ACTIVATION ENERGY OF ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY (kJ mol⁻¹)

Calcination temp. °C	CuO-Fe ₂ O ₃		CuO-Cr ₂ O ₃ E _a
	E _{a1}	E _{a2}	
500	29.3	62.3	19.8
600	29.4	67.5	20.9
700	30.9	74.0	23.6
800	33.2	80.0	26.0

For the $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ system, the $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ plots (Fig. 2) for samples calcined at different temperature (500–800°) show that the conductivity increases

Fig 2. Arrhenius plots of electrical conductivity of $\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ mixture calcined at: (—○—) 500°, (—●—) 600°, (—△—) 700 and (—×—) 800°.

with increasing temperature of calcination which is in agreement with that reported¹³ for the pure and doped chromia samples. The activation energies for the different calcination temperature are also shown in Table 1. Copper chromite is a *p*-type semiconductor and exists in the normal spinel structure¹². The low conductivity in CuCr_2O_4 may be due to the double exchange between Cu^{I} and Cu^{II} and not between Cr^{III} and Cr^{IV} . Goodenough¹⁴ mentioned that Cu^{I} could not be stable in the presence of Cr^{IV} in CuCr_2O_4 . Ballal and Mande¹⁵ showed that the plot of chemical shift (adsorption edge of copper in spinel shifts towards the high energy side of the metal edge) against ionic energy parameter of some compounds containing copper in the structure (such as CuCl_2 , CuTiS_4 , CuCr_2S_4 , CuCr_2Se_4 and CuCr_2Te_4) gave a linear relation for all compounds except CuCr_2O_4 which does not lie on the copper curve as for the other metals. He concluded that this may be attributed to the fact that in CuCr_2O_4 the valency of copper has two different values, Cu^{I} and Cu^{II} , whereas for rest of the compounds it has only one and the same value.

For the $\text{CuS}-\text{Cr}_2\text{S}_3$ system, Fig. 3 shows the $\ln \sigma$ vs $1/T$ plots and that the conductance decreases

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plots of electrical conductivity of $\text{CuS}-\text{Cr}_2\text{S}_3$ mixture calcined at: (—○—) 200, (—●—) 250 and (—△—) 300°.

as the calcination temperature increases up to 250° (reaches a minimum), followed by an increase with further temperature increase up to 300°. This behaviour could indicate that CuCr_2S_4 behaves as metallic conductor in the calcination temperature range 200–250° while at 300° a part of CuS is converted to CuSO_4 , thus leading to an increase in the conductance value. For samples calcined at 200 and 250°, the activation energy values (5.7, 5.2 and 4.2 kcal mol⁻¹ at 200, 250 and 300°) do not change greatly and amount to 5.5 ± 0.2 kJ. Goodenough^{14,16} suggested for copper chromite sulphide in normal spinel, the presence of divalent copper and trivalent chromium ($\text{Cu}^{2+} \text{Cr}^{3+} \text{S}_4^{2-}$) and thus the holes are responsible for the metallic conductivity. Klotgering¹⁷ gave an explanation for the properties of CuCr_2S_4 that is based on the formula $\text{Cu}^+ \text{Cr}^{3+} \text{Cr}^{4+} \text{S}_4^{2-}$. The metallic conduction was attributed to the double exchange between Cr^{III} and Cr^{IV} ions. Klotgering *et al.*¹⁸ modified their model and assumed that the spinel CuCr_2S_4 contained Cu^{I} ion but that the chromium ions were all trivalent. There is a hole in the valence bond, and these holes are responsible for the electrical conductivity and also for the exchange between the chromium ions.

From the electrical conductivity measurements, it could be concluded that CuCr_2O_4 has a lower conductivity than CuCr_2S_4 and CuFe_2O_4 . This may be attributed to the intrinsic conductivity of Cu^{I} and Cu^{II} ions in CuCr_2O_4 spinel. The double exchange between Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} in CuFe_2O_4 could be responsible for conductivity, so the CuCr_2O_4 spinel are semiconductors.

The conduction of CuCr_2S_4 may be due to the presence of excess S^{2-} in the surface, the holes in the valence bond and also due to the double exchange between Cr^{III} and Cr^{IV} .

Reactivity of H_2O_2 decomposition over oxide and sulphide systems : The first order reaction rate was measured in the range 30–50° for the oxide samples calcined at 500, 600, 700 and 800° and the sulphide samples calcined at 200, 250 and 300° (Table 2). It

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANT AND ACTIVATION ENERGY OF H_2O_2 DECOMPOSITION OVER DIFFERENT SYSTEMS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

System	Calcination temp. °C	Rate constant <i>K</i> ($\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$)			E_a KJ mol ⁻¹
		30°	40°	50°	
$\text{CuO}-\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (1 : 1) mol ratio	500	3.01	11.50	24.15	85.0
	600	2.59	9.98	19.16	81.8
	700	0.29	0.74	2.48	87.2
	800	0.13	0.23	0.74	70.5
$\text{CuO}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ (1 : 1) mol ratio	500	1.12	2.36	4.99	60.8
	600	0.88	1.06	2.31	49.6
	700	0.46	0.93	1.81	55.8
	800	0.30	0.62	1.01	49.5
$\text{CuS}-\text{Cr}_2\text{S}_3$ (1 : 1) mol ratio	200	4.60	11.36	32.82	79.9
	250	4.33	9.79	28.71	76.9
	300	7.28	25.52	74.24	94.6

was found that the H_2O_2 decomposition rate constant decreases with increasing calcination temperature for the oxide systems, while it is reverse for the sulphide system. The reaction of Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} ions with H_2O_2 in aqueous solution has been extensively studied¹⁹. The following reaction mechanism seems to fit with the present results.

Initiation step :

Propagation steps :

Termination step :

Similarly, for the Cu^{II} centers, the ionisation of H_2O_2 and $HO_2^{\cdot}$ to form O_2H^- and O_2 respectively, seems to be improbable under the present experimental conditions. From Table 2 it could be concluded that there is no systematic variation in the energy of activation of H_2O_2 decomposition upon changing the catalyst and its temperature of calcination. This indicates that the energy required for the initiation step does not depend only on the type of transition metal atom and its valency state but also upon the position of the atom in the lattice crystal structure and level of lattice imperfections.

For the $Cu-Cr_2O_3$ system, the reaction path suggested for the $CuO-Fe_2O_3$ system is also possible for elements having different oxidation numbers. The activation energies of H_2O_2 decomposition over $CuO-Cr_2O_3$ were calculated (Table 2). The irregular variation in energy of activation for the $CuO-Cr_2O_3$ system shows that the energy required for the initiation step depends upon the nature of catalyst and thermal pre-treatment.

The mechanism of the decomposition of H_2O_2 for $CuS-Cr_2S_4$ system may be similar in path to that previously mentioned for the $CuO-Fe_2O_3$ and $CuO-Cr_2O_3$ systems, where the initiation step could be affected by Cr^{II} , Cr^{III} as well as the higher oxidation states of chromium. The activation energies of the reaction (Table 2) show that there is no systematic variation upon changing the calcination temperature, the values being close to 80 kJ mol^{-1} .

Experimental

The salts used were of AnalaR grade. Mixed oxide (1 : 1) samples ($CuO-Fe_2O_3$, $CuO-Cr_2O_3$) were prepared by calcination of co-precipitated hydroxides from their chloride salts at 500, 600, 700 and 800° for 5 h and subsequent quenching to room temperature. The sulphide system ($CuS-Cr_2S_4$) was obtained by the reported procedure²⁰ through the calcination of co-precipitated sulphides of copper

and thorium salts under isothermal conditions for 5 h at 200, 250 and 300° and subsequent quenching to room temperature.

Chemical analyses of the products were carried out using complexometric method²¹.

Ir absorption spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 599 B spectrophotometer and X-ray diffraction patterns on a Shimadzu diffraction unit using a Cu-target and Ni-filter. Conductivity measurements were made on sample discs (1.3 dia $\times$ 2.7 mm) moulded at room temperature and under a pressure of $2.2 \times 10^3 \text{ kg cm}^{-2}$. Electrical conductivity was measured by coating the sample with silver paste. The sample with holder was heated in an ultrathermostat to a constant temperature in the range, room temperature to $350 \pm 1^\circ$ in air with a Keithly 610 C instrument.

Catalytic activity measurements :

Kinetics of the catalytic decomposition of H_2O_2 were measured as reported earlier²² using solid catalyst (0.1 g) and 0.2 N H_2O_2 (50 ml). The volume of the liberated oxygen was recorded as a function of time.

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